

CALCULATION OF THE ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY OF HOSIERY PRODUCTS MADE FROM SPANDEX YARN WITH DIFFERENT PERCENTAGES

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Annotation. In this article, hosiery products were produced by mixing cotton yarn with different percentages of spandex yarn. Its physical and mechanical properties were analyzed based on standard requirements. The cost of the samples was calculated, their economic efficiency was studied, and recommendations were made.

Keywords: spandex, production efficiency, hosiery products, KJ6F606,

Introduction. Increasing production efficiency in the conditions of market relations is considered an important part of the economic policy of Uzbekistan. The business plan includes a section that considers issues of increasing production efficiency. This section determines the high rates of economic growth in the activities of manufacturing enterprises. It includes a complex of organizational, technical, socio-economic and scientific-research measures aimed at saving social labor. Such measures provide a certain efficiency that allows increasing labor productivity. However, saving material resources from these measures, that is, determining the numerical value of reserves, is a practically difficult issue. To calculate this economic efficiency, it is necessary to have accurate data describing the production process, reflecting the degree of change in certain technical and economic indicators, as well as the final results of one or another measure. These actual results may be calculations taken in the previous year or for a conditional period, that is, for a future period, and they must be expressed in specific values.

Experimental part. During the research, samples of 4 different compositions were obtained on a single-needle 156-needle sock knitting machine of the Chinese company Kejun, model KJ6F606, installed in the "Nam Inno tex Techno" technopark of Namangan State Technical University, and their technological indicators and physical and mechanical properties were studied. In the production of samples, 35 tex cotton yarn was used, and the rubber part was made of 110 d rubber, 100 d polyester and 30/75 d spandex yarn. Initially,

taking into account the fact that cotton yarn has better air permeability and water absorption properties than artificial and synthetic yarns, we produced socks from 100% cotton, aiming to improve the quality of the socks and have a positive effect on human health. Then, taking into account the shape retention and deformation properties, we produced socks samples in the remaining percentages and tested their physical and mechanical properties at the “Textile Products Testing Laboratory” of Namangan State Technical University. The weight of these samples showed different results, which is important in determining the scope of its use.

Percentage and weight of samples

Table 1

Nº	Samples	Weight, g
1	100% cotton	29
2	90% cotton 10% spandex	33
3	80% cotton 20% spandex	25
4	80% cotton 10% spandex 10% polyester	31

Efficiency is a generalizing characteristic of the relationship between the costs and results of economic growth. It means identifying the main directions of increasing production efficiency, knowing some specific quality indicators in production that can affect the overall results of the enterprise's operation, and studying how their changes affect the general indicators of efficiency. As a result of comparing the weight indicators of the resulting hosiery products, it was achieved to reduce the consumption of raw materials in the samples of options I and III compared to the rest. Cotton, spandex, rubber, polyester yarns were mainly used in the preparation of the samples. Since the hosiery product is a piece knit, the proportion of yarns consumed per pair of socks is determined when calculating its raw material consumption.

1kg cotton = 50800 sums

1kg polyester =25000 sums

1 kg spandex = 53340 sums

1kg rubber = 41275 sums

For sample I, the socks made from 100% cotton yarn, the raw material consumption was found as follows.

$$R = (M-2) \cdot N_{1kg} / 1000$$

Here M is the amount of raw material in the share, g

N_{1kg} – the price of 1 kg of raw material, sums

2 – the weight of rubber used in the sock, g (this amount may vary depending on the customer's requirements 2, 3, 4...)

$$R_{rub} = M_{rub} * N_{1kg} / 1000 = 2 * 41275 / 1000 = 82,5 \text{ sums}$$

$$R_{cotton} = (29 - 2) * 50800 / 1000 = 1371,6 \text{ sums}$$

$$R_{total} = R_{cotton} + R_{rub} = 1371,6 + 82,5 = 1454,1 \text{ sums}$$

For sample II, we determine the weight of a sock product made from 90% cotton and 10% spandex yarn by calculating the proportions. Here, Total = 33 gr.

$$M_{cotton} = 90 * 33 / 100 = 29,7 \text{ g}$$

$$M_{spandex} = 10 * 33 / 100 = 3,3 \text{ g}$$

$$R_{rub} = 82,5 \text{ sums}$$

$$R_{cotton} = M_{cotton} * N_{1kg} / 1000 = 29,7 * 50800 / 1000 = 1508,7 \text{ sums}$$

$$R_{spandex} = M_{spandex} * N_{1kg} / 1000 = 3,3 * 53340 / 1000 = 176 \text{ sums}$$

$$R_{total} = R_{cotton} + R_{rub} + R_{spandex} = 1508,7 + 82,5 + 176 = 1767,2 \text{ sums}$$

For sample III, we determine the weight of a sock product made from 80% cotton and 20% spandex yarn by calculating the proportions. Here, Total = 25 g.

$$M_{cotton} = 80 * 25 / 100 = 20 \text{ g}$$

$$M_{spandex} = 20 * 25 / 100 = 5 \text{ g}$$

$$R_{rub} = 82,5 \text{ sums}$$

$$R_{cotton} = M_{cotton} * N_{1kg} / 1000 = 20 * 50800 / 1000 = 1016 \text{ sums}$$

$$R_{spandex} = M_{spandex} * N_{1kg} / 1000 = 5 * 53340 / 1000 = 266,7 \text{ sums}$$

$$R_{total} = R_{cotton} + R_{rub} + R_{spandex} = 1016 + 82,5 + 266,7 = 1365,2 \text{ sums}$$

For sample IV, we determine the weight of a sock product made from 80% cotton, 10% spandex, and 10% polyester yarn by calculating the proportions. Here, Total = 31g.

$$M_{cotton} = 80 * 31 / 100 = 24,8 \text{ g}$$

$$M_{spandex} = 10 * 31 / 100 = 3,1 \text{ g}$$

$$M_{polyester} = 10 * 31 / 100 = 3,1 \text{ g}$$

$$R_{rub} = 82,5 \text{ sums}$$

$$R_{cotton} = M_{cotton} * N_{1kg} / 1000 = 24,8 * 50800 / 1000 = 1259,8 \text{ sums}$$

$$R_{spandex} = M_{spandex} * N_{1kg} / 1000 = 3,1 * 53340 / 1000 = 165,3 \text{ sums}$$

$$R_{polyester} = M_{polyester} * N_{1kg} / 1000 = 3,1 * 25000 / 1000 = 77,5 \text{ sums}$$

$$R_{total} = R_{cotton} + R_{rub} + R_{spandex} + R_{polyester} = 1259,8 + 82,5 + 165,3 + 77,5 = 1585,1 \text{ sums}$$

Conclusion. The research revealed that the samples 1, 3 and 4 we recommend not only have a high amount of raw materials, but also high physical and mechanical properties. The results show that the low cost of hosiery products depends not only on the type of fabric, but also on the proportion of

raw materials. Different proportions lead to a softer product, which, in turn, creates the opportunity to produce more hosiery.

Economic efficiency of the obtained samples

Table 2

Samples	Weight of a pair of socks, g	Price, sums	Number of socks obtained from 1000 kg, pcs.	Maximum cost-effectiveness, pcs.	Efficiency, sums
100% cotton	29	1454,1	34000	4000	5816400
90% cotton 10% spandex	33	1767,2	30000	0	0
80% cotton 20% spandex	25	1365,2	40000	10000	13652000
80% cotton 10% spandex 10% polyester	31	1585,1	32000	2000	3170200

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